

Mild and efficient synthesis of β -amino alcohols by antimony trichloride catalysed opening of epoxides

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Abstract : Nucleophilic opening of epoxides with aniline derivatives in the presence of catalytic amount of antimony trichloride in acetonitrile at room temperature afford the corresponding β -amino alcohols in excellent to very good yield.

Keywords : Epoxide, antimony trichloride, nucleophilic opening, aromatic amine, β -amino alcohols.

Introduction

Epoxides are versatile intermediate in organic synthesis due to their ease of generation and wide reactivity with different nucleophiles such as alcohols, thiols, amines etc. Among the said nucleophiles aromatic amines were paid less attention, probably because of their less reactivity and high affinity towards many Lewis acids. β -Amino alcohols have remarkable synthetic utility because these are used as intermediate in the synthesis of a vast range of biologically active natural products¹ and synthetic amino acids. Some of these compounds are constantly used as β -blockers, insecticidal agents, chiral auxiliaries for asymmetric synthesis² and precursors for oxazoles which have been widely explored as protecting groups³. The classical synthesis of β -amino alcohols consists of heating of epoxides with an excess of amine at elevated temperature⁴. Since the high temperature may not be ideal condition for certain heat labile functional groups, a number of activators have been introduced in the literature to carry out the reaction at room temperature. Thus, many improved procedures have been developed, these include the use of alumina⁵, metal amides⁶, metal alkoxides⁷,

metal triflates⁸, metal halides⁹, silica under high pressure¹⁰, alkali metal perchlorate¹¹, montmorillonite clay under microwave irradiation¹². Very recently, rare earth metal halides¹³ etc. and $\text{Zn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ ¹⁴ have also been used. However, in spite of their potential utility, many of these methods involve expensive reagents, strongly acidic conditions, and difficulty in handling of chemicals and use of promoter like microwave irradiation. Hence a better catalyst is still desirable for nucleophilic opening of epoxide rings by aromatic amines to afford the corresponding β -amino alcohols.

In continuation to our constant effort of exploring the applicability of antimony trichloride (SbCl_3)¹⁵, as a mild Lewis acid in various organic syntheses, herein we report a mild and efficient method for regioselective nucleophilic opening of epoxide rings with amines using this reagent (Scheme 1). As a representative example, we carried out the reaction of styrene oxide (**1a**) with aniline (**2a**) in the presence of SbCl_3 (15 mol%) at room temperature for 1.25 h in dry acetonitrile to furnish the β -amino alcohol derivative **3a** in 91% yield.

Scheme 1

Table 1. Antimony trichloride mediated regioselective ring opening of epoxides by aromatic amines^a

Entry	Epoxide	Nucleophile	Product ^b	Time (h)	Yield (%) ^c
1		1.25	91		
	1a	2a	3a Ar = Ph		
2		1.0	90		
	1a	2b	3b		
3		1.0	85		
	1a	2c	3c		
4		3.0	82		
	1b	2a	3d		
5		3.25	85		
	1b	2d	3e		
6		3.0	86		
	1c	2a	4a		
7		3.0	83		
	1c	2d	4b		
8		2.75	89		
	1c	2c	4c		
9		4.5	91		
	1c	2e	4d		
10		4.5	80		
	1d	2a	4e Ar = C ₆ H ₅		

Table-1 (contd.)

11		Ar = 2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	4.0	75	
	1d	2b	4f		
12		Ar = 3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	4.0	83	
	1d	2f	4g		
13		Ar = 4-Br-C ₆ H ₄	3.50	71	
	1d	2g	4h		
14		1.0	90		
	1e	2h	4i		

^aAll reactions were conducted at room temperature using 15 mol% SbCl₃ in acetonitrile.

^bAll products were characterized by m.p., ¹H and ¹³C NMR and mass spectroscopy.

^cYield refers to isolated pure products and melting points are uncorrected.

Encouraged by this observation, a series of epoxides were subjected to SbCl₃-catalyzed nucleophilic ring opening with aromatic amines and the results are summarized in Table 1. Regioselective ring cleavage in case of aryl oxiranes by a variety of amines with preferential opening from the benzylic position led to single product (entry 1-3). Epichlorohydrin (entry 6-9), glycidyl aryl ethers (entry 10-13) and alkyl oxiranes (entry 14) also underwent cleavage with a variety of amines in a regioselective way at the terminal position to give only one product in each case. Stereochemistry of the ring opening product was found to be *trans* in case of cyclohexyl epoxides (entry 4, 5) as evident from the coupling constants of the methine protons of the cyclohexane ring in ¹H NMR spectra.

In conclusion, we have developed a mild and efficient method for opening of epoxides with various aromatic amines to afford β-amino alcohols. Antimony trichloride was found to be the catalyst of choice in terms of cost, handling, operational simplicity and ease of isolation of products. Moreover, it does not require any promoter or activator such as microwave irradiation. The reactions were very clean and products were obtained in excellent yields without formation of any undesired side product.

Experimental

Representative procedure : To a magnetically stirred solution of epichlorohydrin **1c** (185 mg, 2 mmol) and *m*-nitroaniline **2e** (276 mg, 2 mmol) in acetonitrile (1.5 mL) was added SbCl₃ (69 mg, 0.3 mmol) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 4.5 h. After completion of the reaction (monitored by TLC) the reaction was quenched with water (4 mL) and the resulting mixture was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 20 mL). The extract was washed with water (2 × 5 mL) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue obtained was purified by column chromatography over silica gel (60–120 mesh) using 20% ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (60–80 °C) as eluent to afford **4d** as crystalline solid (420 mg, 91%); m.p. 61 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 3.29 (dd, *J* 7.2, 12.9 Hz, 1H), 3.45 (dd, *J* 3.0, 12.9 Hz, 1H), 3.66 (dd, *J* 6.3, 11.5 Hz, 1H), 3.73 (dd, *J* 4.5, 11.5 Hz, 1H), 4.08–4.17 (m, 1H), 4.40 (brs, 1H), 6.93 (dd, *J* 2.0, 8.1 Hz, 1H), 7.30 (t, *J* 8.2 Hz, 1H), 7.44–7.45 (m, 1H), 7.57 (dd, *J* 1.4, 8.0 Hz, 1H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) δ 46.6, 47.4, 69.8, 106.6, 112.4, 119.3, 129.9, 148.8, 149.2; HRMS calcd. for [C₉H₁₁N₂ClO₃ + Na⁺] 253.0356, found

253.0357.

Spectral data of 4c : Syrupy liquid; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ 2.46 (brs, 1H), 3.21 (dd, J 7.2, 13.1 Hz, 1H), 3.36 (dd, J 4.2, 13.1 Hz, 1H), 3.64 (dd, J 6.2, 11.3 Hz, 1H), 3.70 (dd, J 4.4, 11.3 Hz, 1H), 4.06–4.10 (m, 1H), 6.59 (d, J 8.6 Hz, 2H), 7.14 (d, J 8.8 Hz, 2H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) δ 47.2, 47.6, 69.8, 114.4 (2), 122.8, 129.0 (2), 146.4; HRMS calcd. for $[\text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{NOCl}_2 + \text{H}^+]$ 220.0291, found 220.0299.

Spectral data of 4e : m.p. 59 °C; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ 3.30 (dd, J 7.1, 12.9 Hz, 1H), 3.44 (dd, J 4.1, 12.9 Hz, 1H), 3.78 (s, 3H), 4.00 (dd, J 5.9, 9.4 Hz, 1H), 4.06 (dd, J 4.0, 9.4 Hz, 1H), 4.23–4.25 (m, 1H), 6.69 (d, J 7.9 Hz, 2H), 6.75 (t, J 7.7 Hz, 1H), 6.68–6.89 (m, 4H), 7.20 (t, J 7.8 Hz, 2H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) δ 46.6, 55.7, 68.8, 70.9, 113.2 (2), 114.7 (2), 115.5 (2), 117.9, 129.3 (2), 148.0, 152.5, 154.2; HRMS calcd. for $[\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_3\text{N} + \text{H}^+]$ 274.1438, found 274.1439.

Spectral data of 4g : m.p. 75 °C; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ 3.27 (dd, J 6.9, 12.8 Hz, 1H), 3.40 (dd, J 4.0, 12.8 Hz, 1H), 3.78 (s, 3H), 3.98 (dd, J 6.4, 9.2 Hz, 1H), 4.04 (dd, J 3.9, 9.3 Hz, 1H), 4.20–4.26 (m, 1H), 6.54 (dd, J 1.7, 8.0 Hz, 1H), 6.65 (d, J 1.7 Hz, 1H), 6.69 (d, J 7.8 Hz, 1H), 6.82–6.91 (m, 4H), 7.08 (t, J 8.1 Hz, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) δ 46.3, 55.7, 68.7, 70.8, 111.5, 112.8, 114.8 (2), 115.6 (2), 117.7, 130.2, 135.0, 149.2, 152.4, 154.3; HRMS calcd. for $[\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{NCl} + \text{H}^+]$ 308.1048, found 308.1046.

Spectral data of 4h : m.p. 111 °C; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ 2.51 (brs, 1H), 3.25 (dd, J 7.1, 12.8 Hz, 1H), 3.39 (dd, J 4.3, 12.8 Hz, 1H), 3.78 (s, 3H), 3.98 (dd, J 6.6, 9.5 Hz, 1H), 4.05 (dd, J 5.4, 9.3 Hz, 1H), 4.22 (m, 2H), 6.55 (d, J 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.83–6.88 (m, 4H), 7.26 (d, J 8.7 Hz, 2H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) δ 46.5, 55.7, 68.7, 70.7, 109.5, 114.7 (4), 115.5 (2), 132.0 (2), 147.1, 152.4, 154.3; HRMS calcd. for $[\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{BrNO}_3 + \text{H}^+]$ 352.0543, found 352.0542.

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